

Evidence Based Cured Case of Diabetes Mellitus with Application of Cardinal Principles of Homeopathy : A Case Report

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Abstract

A case of diabetes mellitus hereby presented is an illustration of the application of the cardinal principles of Homeopathy as laid down by Master Samuel Hahnemann in the Organon of Medicine. After careful analysis and repertorisation of the case, homeopathic similimum was prescribed. The patient was regularly followed up for 6 months which showed progressive improvement in blood sugar levels first, followed by improvement in sexual debility. Complete recovery was achieved and confirmed on subsequent follow-up. The case report highlights the beneficial role of individualized homeopathic remedy in treatment of chronic diseases diabetes mellitus through a constitutional approach, aims at the rapid, gentle, and permanent restoration of health, resulting in the complete annihilation of the disease in its whole extent, rather than temporary palliation of symptoms.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, Chronic disease, Cardinal principles of Homeopathy, Holistic homeopathy, Similimum.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent high blood sugar levels. The disease primarily arises due to gradual functional impairment of pancreatic β -cells, leading to insufficient insulin production and altered glucose metabolism later by progressive failure of the cells. Clinically, diabetes presents with characteristic symptoms such as polyuria (frequent urination), polydipsia (excessive thirst), polyphagia (increased hunger), unexplained weight loss, fatigue, and delayed wound healing. If left uncontrolled, it may lead to microvascular and macrovascular complications affecting the eyes, kidneys, nerves, and cardiovascular system. This condition has become a global health concern, with an increasing prevalence worldwide due to rise in sedentary lifestyle, obesity, stress and dietary imbalances, hence working on lifestyle modifications including regular physical activity, balanced nutrition, weight control, stress management and avoidance of tobacco and alcohol play a vital role in prevention and long-term management of diabetes.¹

The true chronic diseases are those that arises from a chronic miasm, which when left to themselves, and unchecked by the employment of those remedies that are specific for them, always go on increasing and growing worse, notwithstanding the best mental and corporeal regime, and torment the patient to end his life with ever aggravated sufferings. These are the numerous and greatest scourges of the human race; for the most robust constitution, the best regulated mode of living and the most vigorous energy of the vital force are insufficient for their eradication.² In Homeopathy, Diabetes is regarded as a chronic disease resulting from derangement of vital force from chronic miasm.

Case History

A 40 year old male consulted in March 2024 for his raised blood sugar levels and informed his recent HbA1c level to be 10.8%. Along with a complaint of Diabetes Mellitus, he had sexual debility, erectile dysfunction with early ejaculation and low back pain, sciatic nerve pain extending to mainly right leg affecting hamstring and calf muscles. Constipation with ineffectual defecation, excessive bloating in abdomen and slow digestion. Sometimes painful swelling of parotid glands if caught seasonal cold and sneezing.

History of presenting complaint

The patient told us that he has been regularly consuming alcohol for about 3 years until one day he experienced episode of vomiting, anxious feeling and blurriness of vision after which he underwent regular health check up where he got to know about his raised blood sugar level beyond normal limits and his shooting HbA1c level. His triglyceride and liver profile SGPT, ALP levels were also raised.

Test name	Values	Biological reference Interval
Average Blood Sugar	263.26	mg/dl
HbA1c	10.8%	4.2-5.7%
Triglycerides	398.5	<150mg/dl
Alkaline Phosphatase	228	38-126 U/L
SGPT	56	5-34 U/L

Table 1. Patient's relevant blood investigation report dated 23/01/2024 (before treatment).

Past History

He had dengue, typhoid, history of injury on his back resulting in low back pain and sciatic nerve pain while playing cricket and renal stones in bilateral kidney.

Family history: Father also had diabetes mellitus, and cardiac issues. Mother had a cholecystectomy surgery and chronic pain in both knees. He was the eldest of all three brothers and his younger brothers had no significant medical history. Grandparents had pancreatic cancer, cardiac issues and brain stroke.

Physical Generals

Hot thermals, thirsty, excessive craving for sweets and aversion to sour-cold things accounting to his frequent complaint of sore throat, incomplete evacuation of stools, excessive easy perspiration, unrefreshing sleep, slow healing of wounds with tendency to suppurate in injuries. He has fear of high places resulting in an anxious state, suffocation in closed space. He had brittle nails and skin is susceptible to fungal infection, rashes in hot humid weather.

Life space and interpersonal history

The patient was born into a nuclear family marked by frequent parental conflicts, which made him feel fearful and emotionally insecure during childhood. As the eldest son, he initially received attention and care, but after the birth of his younger siblings, he felt neglected and abandoned. He enjoyed playing cricket but became overly cautious due to repeated injuries. Although he performed well academically until the 5th standard, his studies declined thereafter due to the stressful home environment and lack of emotional support. After completing the 12th standard, he discontinued further education because of difficulties in concentration and understanding. He began working at a young age in low-paying jobs and currently works as a technical support agent after completing a short training course. Despite aspirations to build a career in the IT sector, ongoing health issues have hindered his progress. He feels he has not achieved his true potential and attributes this to his early family environment and lack of parental support. He has faced financial instability throughout his life. His romantic relationship ended due to financial constraints, and he later entered an arranged marriage where he feels misunderstood and emotionally disconnected. He has no close friends and lacks an emotional outlet, though he continues to fulfill his responsibilities as a husband and father without feeling deeply affectionate. Over time, he turned to alcohol as a coping mechanism, which contributed to the development of diabetes mellitus. He believes that with a more supportive upbringing, he could have achieved much more. He aspires to open a non-profit community kitchen for the underprivileged and establish an old-age home to foster intergenerational connection and care. Dispositionally, he is generally jovial, light-hearted, and cautious, but can become aggressive when things do not go his

way. He is sensitive to conflict, tends to brood over past experiences, and has a strong will, while remaining responsible and persevering in fulfilling his duties.

Selection of rubrics from Analysis of the case:

Based on the above case history, The physical symptoms were common disease symptoms, so we took the marked mental generals with sexual debility. We will use physical generals to rule out other remedies. Repertorisation was done by using RADAR software. Miasmatic analysis of the case : Psoro-sycotic miasm.

Figure 1: Shows the repertorisation sheet along with a close-coming group of remedies

Prescription:

Rx *Calcarea sulphuricum* 200 / 1 single dose was given on 11/03/2024, followed by sac lac for 4 weeks.

The patient was advised to take a few Fasting, Random and Post Prandial Blood sugar readings. The patient was advised to take a few Fasting, Random and Post Prandial Blood sugar readings.

Basis of prescription:

Hot thermals, thirsty, susceptible to boils, abscesses suppuration and glandular affection.³

Calcarea sulphuricum is commonly known as plaster of paris (gypsum), a plaster cast used to immobilise a fractured limb. In addition to a need for stability of *calcarea, sulphur* introduces an element to ego and appreciation to the salt. Hence the main feeling of *Calcarea sulphurica* is that he is not appreciated at the place of security, for example by his parents, hence has delusion, he/she is not appreciated, aversion to people who do not agree with them, egoistic and timid, quarrelsome, angry calcarea.⁴

Follow up

Date	Follow up of the patient	Prescription
16/4/2024	Reduced Fasting Blood Sugar values: 230 - 190 mg/dl. Low back pain persisted, moderate sciatic nerve pain extending to hamstring muscles, sometimes to calves muscle in right leg, Constipation occurred a few days, No change in sexual debility.	Rx <i>Calcarea Sulphuricum</i> 200 / One single dose / Sac Lac for 4 weeks.
25/5/2024	Reduced Fasting Blood Sugar values: 200 - 155 mg/dl. Low back pain much better, moderate sciatic nerve pain sometimes after exertion, pain extending to hamstring muscles only, pain in calves muscle is better, constipation occurred a few days, Mild change in sexual debility. Advice for HbA1c, Lipid profile and KFT.	Rx <i>Calcarea Sulphuricum</i> 200 / One single dose / Sac Lac for 4 weeks.

30/6/2024	Average Fasting Blood Sugar: 128.37 mg/dl HbA1c: 6.1%, Triglyceride: 122.1 mg/dl, ALP: 137 U/L, SGPT: 39 U/L. Blood Reports have improved significantly. Low back pain appears after exertion, otherwise reduced, sciatic nerve pain till hamstring muscle sometimes only. Constipation occurred 2-3 times only, mild change in sexual debility.	Rx <i>Calcarea Sulphuricum</i> 200 / One single dose / Sac Lac for 4 weeks.
10/8/2024	Fasting Blood Sugar values: 110-130 mg/dl. Low back pain much better, relief in sciatic nerve pain extending to hamstring muscles occurred once, no pain in calves muscle, constipation occurred 2-3 times, Mild change in sexual debility.	Rx <i>Calcarea Sulphuricum</i> 200 / One single dose / Sac Lac for 4 weeks.
15/09/2024	Fasting Blood Sugar values: 100-128 mg/dl. Low back pain much better, relief in sciatic nerve pain, no pain in hamstring or calves muscle, constipation also better, no bloating in abdomen, improvement in sexual debility as well. Advice for test: HbA1c, Lipid profile and KFT	Rx Sac Lac for 4 weeks.

Table 2. Follow up and management of the case

However, the patient did not return for follow-up and discontinued his treatment with us. Nearly a year later, he visited again for a consultation regarding his son. During that visit, we advised him to repeat his blood tests so we could monitor his progress. The next blood test was conducted in May 2025.

Date	HbA1c (%)	Avg. glucose-plasma (mg/dl)	Triglycerides (mg/dl)	ALP (U/L)	SGPT (U/L)
23/1/2024	10.8	263.26	398.5	228	56
30/6/2024	6.1	128.37	122.1	137	49
26/5/2025	5.7	116.89	136	104	38

Table 3. Summary of change in blood investigation report of the patient

Figure 2: Attachment of blood investigation report of the patient

Discussion

Diabetes is a chronic disease and its prevalence is much more common. Persistent high blood sugar can cause severe complications over time, if left untreated or unmanaged. Homeopathy focuses on an individualised holistic approach in treatment of diabetes. Treatment as per the guidance of Master Hahnemann mentioned in his book 'Organon of medicine' ensures that we do not treat mere symptoms but the patient as a whole being, to avoid recurrence. This case highlights the application of cardinal principles of Homeopathy in the treatment of diabetes and role of homoeopathy as a safe and effective mode of treatment in not just managing but curing diabetes.

Conclusion

In Homeopathy, Diabetes is regarded as a chronic disease resulting from derangement of vital force from chronic miasm. A detailed case-taking was undertaken for the case presented, following the homeopathic method of individualization, considering the physical generals, mental disposition, and miasmatic background of the patient. The totality of symptoms was formed and a constitutional remedy most similar to the case presented was prescribed. The progress of the case was assessed periodically through clinical symptoms and laboratory investigations, particularly blood glucose levels and HbA1c to evaluate the improvement in both general health and metabolic balance. The patient was regularly followed up for 6 months which showed progressive improvement in blood sugar levels first, followed by improvement in sexual debility. Complete recovery was achieved and confirmed on subsequent follow-up. The case was managed strictly according to the cardinal principles of Homeopathy—namely, the Law of Simila, Law of Simplex, Law of Minimum Dose, and the Doctrine of drug proving, Theory of Chronic diseases, Theory of vital force, The Doctrine of drug dynamisation. Treatment of chronic diseases such as Diabetes Mellitus, when undertaken in accordance with these principles through a constitutional approach, aims at the rapid, gentle, and permanent restoration of health, resulting in the complete annihilation of the disease in its whole extent, rather than temporary palliation of symptoms.

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